

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY
EXPERIENCE OF REGIONS AND CITIES IN IMPLEMENTING
DEMOGRAPHIC AND MIGRATION POLICIES

Khojiboqiyeva Niginakhan Otkir kizi

*Jizzakh branch of the Mirzo Ulugbek National University of Uzbekistan, 4th-level
student of the "Economics" department*

xojiboqiyevanigina@gmail.com

Abstract: *This article examines the experience of cities and regions in implementing demographic and migration policies. Specifically, it analyzes the natural and migratory growth processes of populations, their effects on cities and regions, as well as the specific impacts of demographic policy on population composition, urbanization processes, and migration. Based on these experiences, recommendations are made to develop effective measures for managing internal and external migration.*

Keywords: *Demography, migration policy, cities, regional development, urbanization, migration processes, natural population growth.*

Today, demographic changes and migration processes are crucial aspects of socio-economic development. By studying the experiences at the city and regional levels, countries can improve their migration policies and develop targeted measures for population settlement. Demographic changes in cities and regions significantly impact urbanization, economic opportunities, and the development of social infrastructure.

Demographic Policy is a set of strategies and measures adopted by the state to manage the population size, structure, and distribution. The main goal of this policy is to promote population growth, ensure social stability, and support economic development.

Migration Policy refers to the strategies and measures adopted by the state to manage population migration. The goal of this policy is to regulate migration processes, ensure social integration, and promote economic growth.

Natural population growth and migration processes are key factors in the development of cities and regions. Demographic changes at the regional level are influenced by economic activity, urbanization processes, and the speed at which people move from rural to urban areas. By managing these changes, countries can establish specific developmental directions for cities and regions. For example, in developing countries, a high level of urbanization increases population density, leading to a greater demand for urban infrastructure.

Cities play a significant role in implementing demographic policies. For instance, Singapore has developed various programs to promote population growth. These programs offer family support, as well as benefits in the fields of education and

healthcare. As a result, Singapore has successfully ensured population growth and social stability.

At the regional level, the implementation of demographic policies may face more challenges. For example, in rural regions of Uzbekistan, there are issues of population decline and youth migration. To address these problems, regional development programs and the enhancement of economic opportunities are necessary.

Demographic policy focuses on managing the age structure of the population, birth and death rates, and regional urbanization processes. European countries' experiences show that the aging population is affecting regional economic development. Additionally, in developing countries, managing high birth rates and migration from rural to urban areas is a pressing issue. From this perspective, it is important to consider the unique demographic and economic factors of each region and implement relevant measures accordingly.

Through migration policies, managing population settlement and reducing inter-regional socio-economic inequalities is crucial. For instance, countries like South Korea and Japan are using technological infrastructure to manage labor migration through innovative approaches. The European Union relies on cooperation in managing internal migration processes, which facilitates labor mobility among member states. Furthermore, the main task in managing migration is to reduce demographic inequalities between regions and balance economic development.

Urbanization processes are increasing demand for services such as education, healthcare, and transport in large cities. As cities grow rapidly, the quality of services must also improve to enhance the quality of life. According to China's experience, managing urbanization by building new cities and improving infrastructure can meet the growing demand. Furthermore, the impact of urbanization on social services plays a significant role in economic growth and reducing inter-regional disparities.

In China, urbanization processes have accelerated, and in the past decade, urban population reached almost 60%. The government developed the hukou system to manage urbanization, which allowed rural populations the right to live in cities and access government services. This system has become an effective way to regulate labor migration in China. In Japan, the aging population has become a key aspect of demographic policy. According to 2023 data, more than 29% of the population is over 65, which places a heavy burden on the social security system. To address this issue, Japan has activated policies to attract foreign labor migrants and is attempting to mitigate the effects of an aging population. Within the European Union, the free movement of people has had a positive impact on economic and demographic growth. For example, after Eastern European countries joined the EU in 2004, internal migration within Europe increased, with many migrants from Poland and Romania

moving to Western European countries. This, in turn, contributed to the Western European economy by addressing labor shortages.

The United States' immigration policy has significantly contributed to economic development. In 2020, nearly 14% of the U.S. population growth was attributed to immigration. Skilled professionals from abroad have played a crucial role in contributing to economic growth, particularly in the technological and scientific sectors, helping the U.S. maintain its global leadership position in the economy. South Korea has experience managing migration through high technological development. In 2023, the country introduced technological platforms and AI-based systems for migrant workers, helping maintain labor market balance and proper placement of migrants.

These examples show that each country addresses demographic and migration issues in unique ways, and these experiences can serve as models for other nations.

In successfully implementing demographic and migration policies, it is crucial to analyze the experiences of cities and regions. Cities offer new opportunities and resources, while regions have specific demographic characteristics. Through these experiences, countries can develop effective strategies to promote population growth, ensure social stability, and support economic development. Improving economic and social infrastructure and reducing the gap between cities and rural areas can enhance the quality of life for the population. Governments must focus on managing urban infrastructure, migration processes, and natural population growth to achieve these goals. For this purpose, studying city and regional experiences more deeply and developing effective strategies is an urgent task.

USED LITERATURE:

1. Castles, S., de Haas, H., & Miller, M. J. (2013). *The Age of Migration: International Population Movements in the Modern World*. Palgrave Macmillan.
2. Kourtit, K., Nijkamp, P., & Stough, R. R. (2011). *Drivers of Urban Development in the 21st Century: A Comparison of Global City Regions*. Springer.
3. Gans, H. J. (2002). *Urban Villagers: Group and Class in the Life of Italian-Americans*. The Free Press.
4. Skeldon, R. (2006). "Interlinkages between Internal and International Migration and Development in the Asian Region". *Population, Space and Place*, 12(1), 15–31.
5. Zhou, M., & Logan, J. R. (2003). "Increasing Diversity and Persistent Segregation: Challenges of Rising Immigrant Populations in America". *Urban Studies*, 40(5-6), 1995-2020.